

Robust Decentralized Context-Aware Sensor Fault Detection with In-Place Self-Calibration

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Abstract—There is a high demand in advanced fault detection methods suitable for sensor networks monitoring complex dynamic systems such as industrial plants or large infrastructure units. This paper proposes a robust and efficient decentralized sensor fault detection method with in-place sensor self-recalibration capability that extracts and uses complex context information referred to the full monitored process. The method includes three main components, all decentralized and sharing the same statistical framework: 1) a consensus-based modeling step based on decentralized RANSAC; 2) a statistical analysis based on Bayesian networks and Hidden Markov Models in which each sensor identifies inconsistencies with the consensus model and determines if it is correctly calibrated, uncalibrated or faulty and; 3) a final step in which each uncalibrated sensor self-recalibrates using the consensus model. The proposed method is efficient in the use of computational and communicational resources, it is scalable and robust against outliers, transmission errors, sensor failures and network topology changes. It has been extensively validated in an experimental industrial setting.

I. INTRODUCTION

The monitoring of most industrial plants is performed by sensors gathering measurements in an unattended way for long periods of time under potentially bad conditions, originating frequent sensor failures and calibration errors. Manual recalibration or substitution of sensors located at inaccessible locations is costly and dangerous. This paper is within the context of the EU-H2020 AEROARMS project dealing with advanced aerial manipulation, in which an aerial robot equipped with two arms is used to autonomously replace faulty sensors installed at inaccessible locations, see Fig.1. We are interested in developing a method capable of robustly and efficiently detecting uncalibrated sensors –and autonomously calibrating them, and also capable of detecting the faulty sensors to be replaced.

Although a number of sensor diagnosis techniques have been developed, they provide only partial solutions unsuitable for the above applications. The great majority of existing methods assume that the measurements gathered by the sensors follow very simple models, in most cases assuming a high density of sensors gathering measurements of a magnitude that is spatially static or with very low spatial variations [1]. These methods are unsuitable for monitoring industrial plants, in which a low number of sensors is used to monitor complex systems. Most methods detect sensors that provide inconsistent measurements but very few can differentiate between faulty or uncalibrated sensors [2], [3]. Besides, very few methods have recalibration capability.

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This paper presents a fully decentralized method that autonomously detects the sensors that provide inconsistent measurements differentiating between uncalibrated and faulty sensors and recalibrating uncalibrated sensors. It extracts and uses complex context information referred to the full monitored process and is suitable for complex processes with linear or non-linear models. The method is divided into three fully decentralized components, all sharing the same statistical framework. First, each sensor obtains an explicit model of the full process being monitored using a distributed RANSAC method (De-RANSAC, [4]) that is robust to outliers. Second, each sensor implements an analysis based on Bayesian Networks and Hidden Markov Models to compute its probability of being faulty, correct or uncalibrated using the consistency of its measurements with the consensus model. Finally, each sensor which uncalibration probability is higher than a threshold self-recalibrates using the consensus model. The method is efficient in the use of resources, scalable and is robust against the main failures that can be found in sensor networks: outlying measurements, transmission errors, sensor failures and network topology changes.

Fig. 1: Cement factory near Sevilla, experimentation site for the AEROARMS project.

The paper is structured as follows. Section II summarizes the main related work. Section III presents the definition of our problem and the main components of the method. Section IV briefly describes the method components. The method performance and robustness is analyzed in Section V. Section VI presents the main conclusions.

II. RELATED WORK

The fragility of individual sensors has motivated intense research efforts in sensor fault detection. Instead of an exhaustive description of existing methods we focus on the works directly related to the key contributions of our scheme.

Many methods employ context information to determine whether a sensor is calibrated or not. This context is usually

extracted from comparing each sensor’s measurements with those of its neighbors assuming high sensor density and that the measurements from all the sensors have similar values [5], [1], [2] or similar evolution along time [6], [3]. The sensors that do not follow the tendency are marked as faulty using a variety of statistical approaches. These methods are very interesting in applications such as environmental monitoring, where there is low spatial variation of measurements, but cannot manage context information provided by measurements following complex models. Our method uses context information referred to the full monitored process without needing high sensor densities. Methods such as [1] seek to reduce this sensor density, but also assume that all the sensors gather similar measurements.

Many existing methods rely on consensus to determine if a sensor is faulty or not. In most of them the consensus is simply found by averaging the measurements gathered by all sensors [7], [8]. In the most complex methods the consensus is based on the least squares method [9], [6]. However, least squares is not robust to outliers: it is not suitable in a problem where outlying measurements from faulty sensors are expected. Our method adopts the decentralized RANSAC method proposed by [4] for building accurate outlier-robust consensus models capable of capturing complex relations between the measurements gathered by different sensors.

Existing methods detect inconsistent sensors but, to the best of our knowledge, only [10] can differentiate between uncalibrated or faulty sensors. Moreover, the method in [10] can only detect simple sensor faults, such as when the sensor provides the same static measurement (stuck-at fault). Our method can differentiate between uncalibrated and faulty sensors and adopts a general sensor model capable of detecting a wide variety of faults (stuck-at fault, abnormal noise level, random measurements faults, among others). Many methods interpret sensor inconsistencies as decalibrations [2], [11], [3], [6], but very few address sensor recalibration. Besides, the few methods that include recalibration only solve it for constant or dynamic offsets [10] disregarding slope recalibration, which is needed in many cases. Our method differentiates between offset and slope uncalibrated sensors and performs offset and slope self-recalibration.

Many methods rely on a central node that performs all or most calculations after receiving the measurements gathered by all the sensors [3], [6], [12], [13]. They usually include strategies to reduce the number of communications, but are not robust to errors in the central node. Our method is fully decentralized: each sensor builds its own consensus process model; classifies itself as calibrated, uncalibrated or faulty and; self-recalibrates if necessary.

III. GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Consider a set of nodes endowed with sensing, computational and communication capacities deployed at known locations –potentially inaccessible– periodically gathering measurements for monitoring a complex process, e.g. the temperature profile along a pipe. Sensor nodes is actually the most frequently-employed technology in industrial process

monitoring, see e.g. [14]. They typically operate in an unattended manner for long periods of time under potentially bad meteorological conditions, resulting in not infrequent failures and calibration errors. Our objective is to develop an integral solution for autonomous sensor-based monitoring of complex systems with in-place self-recalibration capability.

In our method the sensors that are within the same process organize into a cluster, simplifying communications and enabling simultaneous monitoring of several processes in the same environment. Nodes within a cluster are assumed connected –single or multi-hop connections–, although our method is robust to disconnections and transmission errors as shown in Section V. As in most process analysis and monitoring schemes, we assume that the process being monitored is partially known: the model structure is available but the model parameters are unknown and can have changes, e.g. due to meteorological or day/night conditions. The locations of sensors are assumed known or estimated using an aerial robot with methods such as [15]. As in any consensus-based method, we assume that many of the sensors monitoring the process are correctly calibrated. As shown in Section V our method performs well when up to 65% of the sensors are uncalibrated. Measurement noise is assumed Gaussian and statistically independent.

Each sensor gathers one measurement every $T1$ seconds. Our method is executed periodically every $T2$. We will use t to refer to each time a measurement is gathered, and n , to refer to each time the method is executed. The method is composed of three main steps. First, the sensors execute a distributed consensus-based process model computation robust to outliers. Second, each sensor implements an statistical analysis based on Bayesian networks and Hidden Markov Models to compute its probability of being faulty, correct or uncalibrated using the consistency of its measurements with the consensus model. Finally, if the uncalibration probability of a sensor is higher than a threshold, 75% in the performed experiments, it self-recalibrates using the consensus model.

IV. THE PROPOSED METHOD

A. Decentralized process consensus-model computation

In our method the model structure is assumed known. The objective is to robustly determine the parameters of the actual model that best fit with the measurements from all the N sensors involved in monitoring the process, including those faulty or uncalibrated. We adopted the Decentralized Random Sample Consensus (De-RANSAC) algorithm [4], a decentralized iterative method in which each sensor computes its version of the consensus model from a set of measurements potentially containing outliers. De-RANSAC is composed of three stages. First, each sensor computes using Least Squares with its last W measurements several hypotheses of the consensus model parameters and shares them with the rest of the sensors. Second, an iterative distributed voting scheme is employed to decide the hypotheses with more inlying measurements. Finally, a distributed averaging rule is employed to determine the final model parameters using only the inliers. The three iterative stages

stop when they converge avoiding unnecessary calculations. De-RANSAC can determine the parameters of complex models with high robustness against outliers; requires only one-hop communications and; is robust against transmission errors, sensor and node failures and topology changes [4].

Next, each sensor k obtains an statistical characterization of the consensus process model, which is assumed Gaussian since it was obtained from Gaussian measurements using Least Squares. The mean μ_k for sensor k is taken as the value of the consensus model at the position of sensor k . The variance is determined using μ_k and the measurements from all sensors that were assigned as inliers in the computation of the consensus model:

$$\sigma^2 \approx \frac{1}{\sum_{k=1}^N (W_k^* - 2) \sum_{i=1}^{W_k^*} (z_{k,i}^* - \mu_k)^2}, \quad (1)$$

where $z_{k,i}^*$ is inlying measurement i from sensor k , $W_k^* \leq W$ is the number of inlying measurements from sensor k and N is the number of sensors employed in process monitoring. The computation of σ^2 is distributed: each sensor k computes $\sum_{i=1}^{W_k^*} (z_{k,i}^* - \mu_k)^2$ and shares it with the rest. The distributed computation of σ^2 in presence of transmission errors results in different values for each sensor k . Hence, we will use σ_k^2 .

B. Bayesian analysis

Each sensor k performs two stages. First, it evaluates the consistency of its measurements versus the process consensus model. Two types of consistency are analyzed: mean consistency, i.e. the consistency of each of its last W measurements with the consensus mean μ_k and; variance consistency, i.e. the consistency of the variance of its last W measurements with the consensus variance σ_k^2 . Second, with these consistency probabilities each sensor k computes its probability of being correct, uncalibrated or faulty using a Hidden Markov Model (HMM). Figure 2 shows an example where 11 sensors gather temperature readings from a process and build a logarithmic consensus model. The model μ_k and $\pm 3\sigma_k$ interval are shown. The readings from $k=2$ are mean inconsistent and those from $k=5$ and $k=7$ are variance inconsistent.

Fig. 2: Consensus logarithmic model computed by 11 sensors. The measurements from $k=2$ are mean inconsistent and those from $k=5$ and $k=7$ are variance inconsistent.

The mean consistency probability of measurement $z_{k,t}$ gathered by sensor k at time t is estimated with the Bayesian Network shown in Fig. 3-left. $C_{k,t}$ is the consistency of

$z_{k,t}$ with the consensus model mean μ_k . $P(C_{k,t} = 1)$ is the probability that $z_{k,t}$ is mean consistent, and $P(C_{k,t} = 2)$, the mean inconsistent probability. X_t is the state of the system represented by the consensus model μ_k and σ_k^2 . $Z_{k,t}$ is a random variable representing the possible values of $z_{k,t}$. In the Bayesian Network it is simple to obtain the following probability distribution:

$$P(C_{1,t}, C_{2,t}, \dots, C_{N,t}, Z_{1,t}, Z_{2,t}, \dots, Z_{N,t}, X_t) = P(X_t) \prod_{j=1}^N P(C_{j,t}) P(Z_{j,t}|C_{j,t}, X_t) \quad (2)$$

Fig. 3: Simplified schemes of the Bayesian Network for measurement consistency analysis (left) and the Hidden Markov Model (HMM) for sensor diagnosis (right).

Marginalizing on every sensor except k we obtain:

$$P(C_{k,t}, Z_{k,t}, X_t) = P(X_t) P(C_{k,t}) P(Z_{k,t}|C_{k,t}, X_t) \quad (3)$$

Using the Bayes Theorem, we have the expression:

$$P(C_{k,t}|Z_{k,t}, X_t) = P(C_{k,t}) \frac{P(Z_{k,t}, X_t|C_{k,t})}{P(Z_{k,t}, X_t)} \quad (4)$$

Using the Kolmogorov definition $P(Z_{k,t}, X_t|C_{k,t})$ can be expressed as $P(X_t) P(Z_{k,t}|C_{k,t}, X_t)$. Combining this result with (4) and using (3) marginalized over $C_{k,t}$, we obtain:

$$P(C_{k,t}|Z_{k,t}, X_t) = P(C_{k,t}) \frac{P(Z_{k,t}|C_{k,t}, X_t)}{P(Z_{k,t}|X_t)} \quad (5)$$

This expression efficiently computes the probability that $Z_{k,t}$ is mean inconsistent. The a priori probabilities $P(C_{k,t})$ are assigned considering previous knowledge from the sensors: $P(C_{k,t}=1)=0.9$ and $P(C_{k,t}=2)=0.1$. The numerator is taken as $P(Z_{k,t}|C_{k,t} = 2, X_t)$, computed as the probability of taking $Z_{k,t}=z_{k,t}$ obtained from the sensor model, or as $P(Z_{k,t}|C_{k,t} = 1, X_t)$, computed as the probability of taking $Z_{k,t}=z_{k,t}$ from a Gaussian probability density function with μ_k y σ_k that represents the consensus model. The denominator is calculated as $P(Z_{k,t}|C_{k,t} = 1, X_t) + P(Z_{k,t}|C_{k,t} = 2, X_t)$. Each sensor computes $P(C_{k,t}=2|Z_{k,t}, X_t)$ for each of its last W measurements.

Also, each sensor also analyzes the inconsistency of the variance of its last W measurements with the consensus variance σ_k^2 . This inconsistency is represented as $C_{k,t}^\sigma$ and is

computed by a Bayesian Network with the same structure as that in Fig. 3-left. In this case we define $\mathbf{Z}_{k,t}$ as a random variable representing the last W measurements collected by sensor k . It is easy to particularize the above expressions, and particularly (5), to compute the variance inconsistency probability $P(C_{k,t}^\sigma=2|\mathbf{Z}_{k,t}, X_t)$. It is not presented for brevity. $z_{k,t}$ is considered mean inconsistent if $P(C_{k,t} = 2|Z_{k,t}, X_t) > \tau_\mu$. The W measurements are considered variance inconsistent if $P(C_{k,t}^\sigma = 2|\mathbf{Z}_{k,t}, X_t) > \tau_\sigma$. In the performed experiments we used $\tau_\mu=0.9$ and $\tau_\sigma = 0.95$.

Next, in each sensor k the results of the Bayesian Networks are input to the Hidden Markov Mode (HMM) shown in Fig. 3-right, which determines the state of the sensor. Each sensor can be in four states: "correctly calibrated", like sensor $k=1$ in Fig. 2, which is represented as $S_{k,n}=1$; "offset uncalibrated", like sensor $k=2$, represented with $S_{k,n}=2$; "slope uncalibrated", like sensor $k=5$, represented with $S_{k,n}=3$ or; "faulty", represented with $S_{k,n}=4$. The input of the HMM for sensor k is $\mathbf{C}_{k,n} = \{C_{k,t-W+1:t}, C_{k,t}^\sigma\}$, the mean consistency of its last W measurements and the variance consistency. Recall that index n represents each execution of the presented method. Since all the values in $\mathbf{C}_{k,n}$ are statistically independent, the probability of having a set of consistency values given the state of the sensor is:

$$P(\mathbf{C}_{k,n}|S_{k,n}) = P(C_{k,t}^\sigma|S_{k,n}) \prod_{i=t-W+1}^t P(C_{k,i}|S_{k,n}) \quad (6)$$

Notice that $P(C_{k,t}^\sigma|S_{k,n})$ and $P(C_{k,i}|S_{k,n})$ are constant probabilities obtained from the sensor and problem knowledge. The evaluation of the HMM in each time n consists of two stages. The first one, prediction, calculates the probabilities of all the possible states of sensor k using the information from previous evaluations. The second, updates this probability using the current $\mathbf{C}_{k,n}$. For notation simplicity we use $\mathbf{S}_{k,n}$ to denote all possible state values, for instance:

$$P(\mathbf{S}_{k,n}|\dots) = \begin{bmatrix} P(S_{k,n} = 1|\dots) \\ P(S_{k,n} = 2|\dots) \\ P(S_{k,n} = 3|\dots) \\ P(S_{k,n} = 4|\dots) \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

With this notation the prediction stage of the HMM is:

$$P(\mathbf{S}_{k,n}|\mathbf{C}_{k,1:n-1}) = \Omega P(\mathbf{S}_{k,n-1}|\mathbf{C}_{k,1:n-1}), \quad (8)$$

where Ω is a matrix with the probabilities of all the possible state transitions, e.g. $\Omega_{1,2}$ stands for $P(S_{k,n}=1|S_{k,n-1}=2)$:

$$\Omega = \begin{bmatrix} 0.65 & 0.35 & 0.35 & 0.02 \\ 0.10 & 0.35 & 0.02 & 0.04 \\ 0.15 & 0.25 & 0.55 & 0.04 \\ 0.10 & 0.05 & 0.08 & 0.90 \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

These values have been selected using the knowledge from the problem. For instance, the probability that a correctly calibrated sensor remains in this state in the next HMM evaluation is not low ($\Omega_{1,1}=0.65$), but it is highly unlikely

that a faulty sensor becomes correctly calibrated ($\Omega_{1,4}=0.02$). The values can also be obtained experimentally using labeled data sets from simulations or manual observation of the system.

$P(\mathbf{S}_{k,n}|\mathbf{C}_{k,1:n-1})$ is initialized with the state *a priori* probability $P(\mathbf{S}_{k,1})$. The update stage of the HMM is:

$$P(S_{k,n}|\mathbf{C}_{k,1:n}) = \frac{P(\mathbf{C}_{k,n}|S_{k,n})P(S_{k,n}|\mathbf{C}_{k,1:n-1})}{P(\mathbf{S}_{k,n}|\mathbf{C}_{k,1:n-1})^T P(\mathbf{C}_{k,n}|\mathbf{S}_{k,n})} \quad (10)$$

Expressions (10) and (8) can be used recursively to estimate the sensors' state probabilities $P(S_{k,n}|\mathbf{C}_{k,1:n})$. Finally, sensor k is classified as offset uncalibrated, slope uncalibrated or faulty if its probability values overtake certain thresholds: ϵ_2 , ϵ_3 and ϵ_4 , respectively. Otherwise, the sensor is taken as correctly calibrated. In the experiments performed we took $\epsilon_2=\epsilon_3=\epsilon_4=75\%$. These probability thresholds were selected experimentally using data sets.

C. Sensor Self-Recalibration

Finally, the sensors that have been classified as offset or slope uncalibrated self-recalibrate using the consensus model. We assume that each sensor k follows the widely-adopted measurement model [16]: $y_{k,t} = A(x_{k,t} + \eta) + B$, where A and B are internal sensor parameters that transform the actual measurement ($x_{k,t} + \eta$) to provide $y_{k,t}$. η is random Gaussian noise. Erroneous values of A and B lead to sensor uncalibration but these values are usually inaccessible or difficult to be changed. In our method $y_{k,t}$ is the input of a measurement conditioning module that obtains the sensor measurement $z_{k,t}$ as follows:

$$z_{k,t} = \alpha y_{k,t} + \beta, \quad (11)$$

where α and β are calibration parameters. Sensor recalibration is performed by substituting the former α and β by the new α and β that solve:

$$\alpha, \beta = \arg \min_{\alpha, \beta} (x_{k,t} - (\alpha z_{k,t} + \beta)) \quad (12)$$

Sensor k , offset uncalibrated and configured with β_{n-1} , recalibrates by computing the new β_n considering the difference between μ_k , the mean of the consensus model at the position of sensor k , and the mean of the last W measurements gathered by sensor k :

$$\beta_n = \beta_{n-1} + \left(\mu_k - (1/W) \sum z_{k,i} \right) \quad (13)$$

For slope calibration, the new α_n is calculated using the ratio between σ_k^2 , the variance of the consensus model, and $Var(z_{k,t})$, the variance of the last W measurements from sensor k :

$$\alpha_n = \alpha_{n-1} \sqrt{\frac{\sigma_k^2}{Var(z_{k,t})}} \quad (14)$$

Notice that using a new α_n modifies $\sum z_{k,i}$ and a new β_n should be computed with (13).

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The proposed system has been experimentally validated for monitoring a heat exchanger in a experimental industrial setting located at the School of Engineering of Seville. The heat exchanger consisted of two concentric tubes of 11 m length. A total of 11 sensor nodes were installed on the outer tube at regular distances of 1 m in order to analyze the efficiency in heat transfer. Each sensor node was composed by a *TelosB* WSN module connected to a *Sensirion SHT11* temperature sensor. In order to enlarge sensor battery lifetimes their transmission power was reduced to the minimum, which was enough for ensuring communication with the sensors' nearest neighbors. For simplicity the sensors in these experiments were deployed equally spaced. This is not a constraint: the method is general for any sensor network deployment. It is also robust to occasional network disconnections as is shown later in this section.

It is known that the temperature profiles along both tubes in concentric heat exchangers follow logarithmic models [17]. Notice that temperature profile models are not perfectly stationary due to changes in ambient conditions, e.g. day/night. The sensors were configured to gather one temperature measurement every $T1=60$ s and to execute the proposed method every $T2=1800$ s. These values are sufficient to capture the model dynamics and the sensor calibration requirements. Besides, $W=30$ was adopted: it was considered sufficient for robustly executing the De-RANSAC algorithm. The probabilities and thresholds used in the Bayesian Networks and HMM were those mentioned in the previous sections. Next the performance, scalability and robustness of the proposed method are analyzed.

A. Performance

We first describe the operation of the proposed method using examples from the validation setting. Figure 2 shows the last W measurements collected by each sensor since the last time the method was executed. First, the consensus model was determined. During the execution of De-RANSAC each sensor transmitted an average of 75 bytes. The mean μ_k and variance σ_k of the resulting consensus model are shown in Fig. 2. Next, using the Bayesian Networks each sensor determined $C_{k,n} = \{C_{k,t-W+1:t}, C_{k,t}^\sigma\}$ analyzing the inconsistency of each of its W measurements with μ_k and, the inconsistency of the variance of the W measurements with σ_k .

The Bayesian Networks considered that all W measurements from sensor $k=2$ except one were mean inconsistent. Their variance was considered consistent with σ_k . The HMM running in sensor k assigned $P(S_{k,n} = 1|C_{k,1:n}) = 0.83 > \epsilon_2$ and classified it as offset uncalibrated. Next, it performed offset recalibration with $\beta_n = \beta_{n-1} + 5.2$. The Bayesian Networks for sensor $k=5$ considered that its measurements were mean consistent but variance inconsistent. The HMM assigned $P(S_{k,n} = 2|C_{k,1:n}) = 0.79 > \epsilon_3$ and classified sensor $k=5$ as slope uncalibrated. Next, it performed slope recalibration $\alpha_n = 0.31\alpha_{n-1}$. Sensor $k=7$ was also classified

as slope uncalibrated and it self-recalibrated with $\alpha_n = 0.22\alpha_{n-1}$.

After $T2$ the proposed method was executed with the new W collected measurements, which are shown in Fig. 4-top. The measurements from $k=2$ and $k=5$ were consistent with the new consensus model but those from $k=7$ were not. The previous slope calibration was not successful: sensor $k=7$ had a hardware problem and its measurements had abnormally high noise level. In this case the HMM in sensor $k=7$ classified it as faulty sensor. Sensors classified as faulty are taken away from the proposed method's calculations: each sensor keeps a list of non-faulty sensors that are monitoring the same process. Figure 4-bottom shows the evolution of the probabilities $P(S_{k,n}|C_{k,1:n})$ that sensor $k=7$ is correctly calibrated ($S_{7,n}=1$), offset uncalibrated ($S_{7,n}=2$), slope uncalibrated ($S_{7,n}=3$) and faulty ($S_{7,n}=4$) in consecutive executions of its HMM. Four consecutive unsuccessful calibrations are enough to detect a faulty sensor.

Fig. 4: Top) Last W measurements gathered by the sensors in Fig. 2 after recalibration and the new resulting consensus model. Bottom) Evolution of the probabilities that sensor $k=7$ is correctly calibrated, offset uncalibrated, slope uncalibrated and faulty in consecutive executions of its HMM.

Table I summarizes the performance of the presented method during 3 months installed in the experimental setting. It was capable of detecting 98.1% of the times a sensor was correctly calibrated ($S=1$) with a false positive rate of only 0.9%. It detected 97.0% of the times a sensor was offset uncalibrated ($S=2$) with a false positive rate of 1.9%. The false positives are originated by small errors in the model building originated for instance by consecutive packet loss. Similar good performance was observed for the detection of slope uncalibrated sensors ($S=3$) and of faulty sensors ($S=4$). Figure 5 shows the measurements collected by all non-faulty sensors in 5 days, for visualization purposes we do not show longer periods. The industrial plant was kept switched on during ~ 6 hours each day. The changes of the process model within each day can be clearly noticed.

	S=1	S=2	S=3	S=4
True Positive Rate (%)	98.1	97.0	94.6	99.3
False Positive Rate (%)	0.9	1.9	2.5	0.7

TABLE I: Sensor state classification performance obtained during 3 months installed in the experimental setting.

Fig. 5: Measurements collected by all non-faulty sensors in five days in the experimental setting.

B. Scalability and robustness

Next, the scalability of the proposed method with the number of sensor nodes is evaluated. The method was implemented in ROS in order to enable large-scale realistic simulations. We assumed the same sensor setting and industrial process: sensors distant 1 m one another along the external tube of a concentric heat exchanger. All the parameters employed –transmission ranges and transmission error rates, among others– were obtained from the real experiments. Figure 6 shows the total traffic –in number of bytes– transmitted by each sensor assuming settings with between 5 and 500 sensors. The presented results for each setting were obtained averaging 100 different simulations. The proposed method was compared to *Method1*, a centralized scheme such as [6] in which a base station receives measurements from all sensors and performs all computations. It was also compared to *Method2*, a scheme in which the sensor located at the center of the setting receives measurements from the rest of the sensors. The proposed method has lower data traffic and better scalability due to its decentralized approach. Our method is computationally efficient and can be executed in real time even in low-cost sensor nodes. The computational burden in each sensor is almost constant with the number of sensors. There is a slight increment caused by the higher number of iterations required by De-RANSAC to converge.

Robustness against transmission errors is critical in decentralized methods. We analyze robustness to transmission errors using the measurements logged by each sensor in the experimental validation during three months randomly simulating different the packet reception ratios, $PRR \in [0,1]$. Figure 7 shows the true positive rates for detecting sensors correctly calibrated ($S=1$), offset uncalibrated ($S=2$), slope uncalibrated ($S=3$) and faulty ($S=4$) with different PRR s. These results were obtained averaging 100 repetitions for each PRR value. It also shows the false positive probabilities. It can be noticed that our method is rather insensitive to

Fig. 6: Number of bytes transmitted by each sensor in the proposed method, *Method1* and *Method2* when the number of sensors are in the range [5-500].

transmission errors until $PRR < 60\%$.

Fig. 7: Robustness of the proposed method against transmission errors: probabilities of correctly detecting uncalibrated and faulty sensors (top) and false positive probabilities (bottom) with different PRR values.

Consensus-based fault detection methods require that many of the sensors employed are correctly calibrated. Next, we analyze the performance of our method in case of having different percentages of correctly calibrated sensors. We use the measurements logged in the experiments and simulate that different percentages of randomly selected sensors are uncalibrated. Figure 8 shows the true positive rates of correctly detecting the sensor states $S=\{1, 2, 3, 4\}$ obtained averaging 100 different simulations. The method operates robustly when more than 65% of the sensors are correctly calibrated. Notice that it is extremely infrequent to have more than 35% of the sensors uncalibrated at the same time. Also, the performance degrades smoothly until only 40% of the sensors are correctly calibrated.

The proposed method is also robust to topology changes and disconnections. Shortly after sensor $k=7$ in Fig. 4 was classified as faulty, it stopped transmitting and forwarding measurements, dividing the network into two parts. Both parts of the network behaved independently computing different De-RANSAC consensus models but the full func-

Fig. 8: Performance of the proposed method (probabilities of correctly detecting uncalibrated and faulty sensors) with different percentages of correctly calibrated sensors.

tionality of the proposed method was kept. Figure 9 shows the resulting consensus models obtained after the topology change, evidencing robustness against topology changes.

Fig. 9: Consensus models computed independently by each sub-net after the failure of sensor $k=7$.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This work is motivated by the need for advanced sensor fault detection methods suitable for sensor networks monitoring complex systems such as in industrial plants or large infrastructure units. This paper presents an integral solution for autonomous sensor-based monitoring of complex systems with in-place self-recalibration capabilities.

In our method each sensor uses complex context information of the process being monitored to determine its calibration state and to self-calibrate if necessary. It is composed of three main components, all are fully decentralized and within the same statistical framework. First, each sensor participates using De-RANSAC in the computation of an outlier-robust consensus model of the process being monitored. Second, using Bayesian networks and Hidden Markov Models each sensor estimates its probability of being faulty, correct or uncalibrated using the consistency of its measurements with the consensus model. Finally, if a sensor is found uncalibrated in offset or in slope, it self-recalibrates using the consensus model. The presented method is robust to outlying measurements, sensor failures, transmission errors and network topology changes; makes efficient use of computational and communications resources and; has good scalability. Its performance has been extensively validated with experimental results and with simulations.

The presented method can be extended with low modifications to a wide variety of more elaborated monitoring problems. First, it can be used for processes with non-linear process models simply by employing a non-linear

Least Squares algorithm (e.g. Levenberg-Marquardt) instead of Least Squares in De-RANSAC. It can also be employed to monitor 2D or 3D industrial processes (e.g. the temperature profile in a concentrating solar power plant) by using higher-dimensional process models. Moreover, the method can be applied also to processes with discontinuous models if the discontinuity regions are previously mapped, which is a feasible assumption for industrial plants. Implementation and demonstration in a real industrial process is under current work.

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